

(1)Title and Details

(A)Title

Faris' Zeroth Force Law and Motion Equation

(B)Author Information

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(2)Short Summary

“The General Motion Equation actually gives Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation which then gives Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation and all other physical quantities and by these last two things whole reality is described through Classical mechanics in the same way as Relativistic mechanics do as one example.”

(3)Keywords

(1)Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation

(2)Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation

(3)Without mass General Motion Equation

(4)Faris'-Newton Mass Motion Equation instead of force

(5)The Conversion between all three main equations

(6)The Quote about Reality

(4)Statements and Declarations

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No, I declare that the authors have no competing interests or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

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I am Mirza Faris Ahmad.The only Author and Researcher of this Research Paper.

(5)Faris' Zeroth Force Law and Motion

Equation

(A)Introduction

Faris' Zeroth force law is needed to complete the force laws equation and generalising it to n time derivatives. Faris' Zeroth Gravitation Force law is added to combine gravitation laws equation. First equation is converted to second and it is shown how the first equation is derived from a general motion equation that acts as a fundamental to all equations.

(B)Headings

1.Faris' Zeroth Force Law (Force Source)

“The Force is provided by the potential energy of a system.”

Note:I worked on three laws of Force by Newton and published an article named “The Force Laws” and now I am presenting Zeroth Force Law.

Explanation:

The more the system has the stored energy named potential energy the Force produced by this energy will be greater and the question comes why the stored energy specifically then simply because the more the system has stored energy the more it can apply Force there is only need of some stored energy as you can assume by common sense for Force. The Newton's First Law of Force is Force physical explanation, Newton's Second Law of Force is Force Mathematical Explanation, Newton's Third Law of Force is a generalization to N forces and Faris' Zeroth Law of Force completes this set by providing the Force source. Hence Physical and mathematical Explanation of N forces along with Force source is a complete set of Force Laws named Faris'-Newton Force Laws. The combined laws equation is also mentioned in my article named “The Force Laws”.

Equation

$$U \propto F$$

$$U = Fd$$

Note:Where d is proportionality constant.

Explanation:As the potential energy of a system increases its capability to apply large force increases also. The proportionality constant d is for dimensional sense.

The Combined Force Laws Equation

The Combined Laws Equation of Force by Newton will include Faris' Zeroth Law of force Equation also. One can do this by a simple substitution for Force in the Combined Laws equation and hence writing U/d instead of F in Combined Laws Equation but only for action forces and ma for the reaction forces but ma for action forces and U/d for reaction forces will be equivalent.

2.Faris' Zeroth Law of Gravitation Force

“The Gravitation Force is provided by the potential energy of a star.”

Note:I mentioned three laws of Gravitation Force in my article named “Faris’-Newton Gravitation Force Laws”. The first two laws of Gravitation Force by me are similar to the first and third law of Force by Newton while Newton's Law of Gravitation Force is similar to Newton’s Second Law of Force.

Explanation:

The more the star has stored energy named potential energy its capability of applying attraction force or Gravitation Force increases as this is also not difficult to see by common sense.

The Faris' First Law of Gravitation Force is physical explanation of Gravitation Force, Newton's Law of Gravitation is mathematical explanation of Gravitation Force, Faris' Second Law of Gravitation Force is a generalization to N Gravitation forces and Faris' Zeroth Law of Gravitation Force completes this set by providing Gravitation Force source. The physical and mathematical explanation of Gravitation Force along with its generalization to N Gravitation forces by giving the Gravitation Force source is a complete description of Gravitation Force. These laws are together named as Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws. The combined laws equation is also mentioned in my article named “Faris’-Newton Gravitation Force Laws”.

Equation

$$U \propto F_g$$

$$U = F_g d$$

Note:Where d is proportionality constant.

Explanation:As the potential energy of a star increases its capability to apply Gravitation Force also increases.Where d is proportionality constant for dimensional sense.

The Combined Gravitation Force Laws Equation

Combined Laws equation of Gravitation Force by me and Newton as I mentioned in my previous article will also include a Equation of Zeroth Law of Gravitation Force.The substitution for F_g in Combined Laws equation by U/d is a simple way.

Note:

The conversion from Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation to Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation is simple.Substitute $g=Gm_2/r^2$ in Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation and you will get Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation.Actually Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation is Newton's Second Force Law Equation and Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation is simply Newton's Gravitation Force Law Equation and by comparing these two equations one get the value of g that is used for conversion.

3.Motion Equations

As for the ideal case a velocity-time graph of moving object with uniform acceleration is a straight line originating at the midpoint of y axis and making an elevation angle with horizontal.Consider y increment of line to be Δv and x increment to be t.The line has ends therefore there is a triangle in graph and since the line originate from midpoint of y axis the triangle is sitting on a rectangle.This triangle and rectangle together acting as a trapezoid.

First

The first motion equation will be simply the slope of the graph line.

Equation

$$a = \frac{dv}{dt}$$

Second

The second equation will be simply the area under the graph line called the total distance covered which is the sum of area of triangle and area of rectangle.

Equation

$$r = v_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta v t$$

Third

The third equation will be simply the area under the graph line called the total distance covered which is the area of trapezoid.

Equation

$$r = \frac{v_f^2 - v_i^2}{2a}$$

Note: The above results about motion equations are already known to everyone and they are very old hence it is not needed to explain them.

4. General Motion Equation (Nth time derivative)

If you see that the motion equations written before consider acceleration constant (condition to find displacement covered stated as first motion equation which is actually formula for acceleration) and gives two different equations of position function (the displacement covered equations are stated as second and third motion equation). To generalize motion equations you have one long method by considering again the jerk uniform and evaluate two different equations for velocity and the short method is by differentiating position function equation. The generalisation done in this way is actually generalization of motion equations to n time derivatives.

Equations

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(\frac{v_f^2 - v_i^2}{2a} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(v_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta v t \right)$$

(C) Discussion

1. The different Motion Equations

Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation of Motion and General Motion Equation are distinct. Generalisation of Faris'-Newton Force Laws is needed to n time derivatives since it is only valid for second time derivative. Generally Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation can be called Faris'-Newton Mass Motion Laws Equation and to generalize mathematically replace a in Faris'-Newton Force Laws Equation with nth time derivative of position function and remember now this equation

represent mass motion therefore includes mass along with nth position function time derivative but motion equations are just representing nth position function time derivative without mass so only difference is mass.

Equation

Mass Motion Equation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) \right)_i = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{V_j}{d_j}$$

Without Mass Motion Equation:

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(\frac{v_f^2 - v_i^2}{2a} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(v_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta v t \right)$$

Note: Where F is replaced by M when a is replaced by nth position function time derivative and U is replaced by V when F is replaced by M.

2. Conversion between Motion Equations

If you multiply without mass motion equation by m on both sides and compare it with mass motion equation and get a value for V then substituting that value of V in mass motion equation gives you without mass motion equation. Hence converting without mass motion equation to with mass motion equation is also possible.

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-Faris

(D)Importance

The description of motion as given in this article gives a way to interpret things in a much broader way than before.

(E)Abbreviations

I have written potential energy but not work since the word potential energy looks more appropriate here.

(F)Prediction

It has great importance in Classical mechanics because a deep look at following equation implies many things:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) \right)_i = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{V}{d}$$

If you see the above equation then the first time derivative at left hand side is momentum. In the same way the third time derivative at right side transforms V to power. In this way Faris'-Newton Mass Motion Laws Equation gives backs almost all of the physical quantities of Classical mechanics.

(G)Conclusion

First i presented Zeroth Force Law then i presented Zeroth Gravitation Force Law and combined both equations with their combined laws equation. Then I generalized Motion equations to n time derivatives. At the end i showed how to convert between motion equations.